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NOD2 control of OX40.

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We describe here a biologically important interaction between the NLR and TNF superfamily, as evidenced by NOD2 control of OX40, a co-stimulatory TNF receptor with described functions in exhaustion. The data together provide evidence that a central function of innate immune NLR-mediated signaling is maintenance of homeostasis in the immune system by enforcing tolerogenic signaling by control of exhaustion program gene expression.